

LAW-MAKING PROCESSES IN THE UNITED STATES GOVERNMENT

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The Role of the Congress in Law Making

The Congress is the United States lawmaking body. It writes and enacts laws. The laws designed and enacted in the Congress are designed to protect personal or civil liberties of the citizens of the United States and keep them safe. The lawmaking process is designed to be slow, complicated and cumbersome. The three government branches, namely, the executive, the judiciary and the legislature all work together and share power as designed in the checks and balances model that ensures that no arm of the government has too much power than others .

The United States Congress has two complementary bodies; the Senate and the House of Representatives. The house of representatives receives more representatives from most populous states, that is, the more the number of people in the state, the more representatives that it sends to the House of Representatives. The Senates houses two representatives per state. This ensures that, in the lawmaking process, the majority of the representatives will reflect the will of the many citizens they represent in the houses.

The legislative process in the House of Representatives is similar to that in the Senate. The only difference is the House of Representatives operates with more people. Once a bill is passed in the House of Representatives or the Senate, it goes to other chambers for passage. A substantive change in the bill means the bill goes back to the respective house for approval. This means that one chamber can pass a bill, but if another fails to pass it, there are chances the bill will die or stall. If a bill passes through both chambers of the Congress, it goes straight to the president for assent. The president can either sign it into law or exercise his veto powers in the form of checks and balances. The Congress can override the presidential veto by two-thirds majority vote.

The Role of the President in Law Making

In the United States, the president is the head of state and government. He is the commander in chief of the armed forces and the head of the executive of the federal government. The president is considered to be among the most powerful political figures in the world, and the leader of the only global superpower (Cooper, 2014). The president of the United States controls the world most expensive military, the world's largest economy, and the second largest nuclear weaponry. The powers of the executive are vested on the president (Wilson, 2017). These powers include execution and enforcement of the federal laws, the appointment of executives, regulatory, judicial officers and diplomats and signs treaties with other countries in consultation with the Senate of the United States. He also has the powers to grant federal reprieves and pardons. He is further empowered to adjourn or convene both houses of the congress. He, besides, has the powers to veto or sign the federal legislation. The powers of the president and the federal government have grown substantially since its formation.

In the lawmaking process, any bill passed by the Congress must be presented before the president for assent before it becomes law. The president has three options to take on the bill presented before him. He signs the law within ten days and becomes law, vetoes the legislation with a ten-day time frame and returns it to the Congress with objections. The bill fails to become law unless the Congress overrides the veto by two-thirds majority vote. The president has also the option of taking no action on the legislation within the ten-day time frame. The bill, therefore, becomes law by default; unless the Congress is adjourned at the time, a fact known as the pocket veto.

The Role of Bureaucracy in Law Making

The federal bureaucracy in the United States government represents the civil service that inspires revulsion and admiration as a feature through professionalism, helpfulness, and responsiveness in its service delivery. This is unlike many nations in the world where bureaucracy can be replaced by inefficiency, red tape, corruption, and government overreach. The federal bureaucracy is considered an essential component of the federal system in the United States (Wilson, 2017). It has also been referred to as the fourth arm of the federal government. For the successful running of the government regarding improving the quality of life, enhancing economic growth and provision of public goods, the government uses bureaucracy in taxation, homeland security, immigration, foreign affairs and education (Neubauer & Meinhol, 2016). Public policy implementation by government bureaucrats and the academic study constitute public administration and prepare civil servants for work in government departments.

The federal bureaucracy plays a significant role in the creation of laws. The congress leaves leeway while making laws because it lacks the expertise that can apply in some areas. These leeways are filled by the federal bureaucracy. It also makes rules that affect how programs operate, and these rules are subject to enforcement, just like laws (Neubauer & Meinhol, 2016). The federal bureaucracy also implements policies made by the executive and the Congress. Through enabling legislation, an agency in the federal bureaucracy is granted the power to work out specifics. This, though, must be done within certain boundaries. They also administer policy since they know much more than the president or the Congress does. This adds to the bureaucrats' powers.

The Role of Courts in Law Making

The courts have a unique role in the lawmaking process. The judiciary checks the Congress and the president. The Supreme Court can declare a law either the House of Representatives or the Senate unconstitutional and therefore cannot become law. It can also outlaw the unconstitutional or unlawful actions of the president. It also has the power to declare an unconstitutional law passed by a state unconstitutional and therefore null and void. The Supreme Court has the final say on the validity, and legality of laws passed on the Congress. It is also the final judge in cases about the constitution which is the highest law of the land.

The courts of the United States ensure that the constitution is duly followed and enforced. The courts also ensure that the lawmakers and the policymakers exercise their powers within a certain boundary set by the constitution. The judiciary of the US is among the world's most extensive. It serves to correct the government officials and their roles in law and policy making whenever they step out of bounds. The Congress, the state police, and other government officials must obey the orders of the courts of the United States. This is done to ensure that there is the rule of law in the country to prevent power backlash among the arms of the governments. The judiciary of the United States is just as powerful as the presidency and the legislature. In the checks and balances model, the judiciary is audited and regulated by the presidency as the president appoints the head of the Supreme Court and the larger judiciary.

The Role of Interest Groups in the Law-Making Process

Interest groups have a crucial role to play in the lawmaking process in many countries around the world, including the United States. These are groups that are highly organized, made up of citizens and experts advocating for a cause (Wilson, 2017). The United States homes

thousands of interest groups, each investing a lot of time, resources and efforts for their supporters and the United States citizens at large, including the minority groups. These interest groups have specializations; some make sure that people benefit from quality healthcare, wage raises, education and many other vital roles they play. Many steps concerning freedoms are a direct result of interest groups. Interest groups are categorized into four: anomic, associational, non-associational and institutional. Anomic are ad hoc and unplanned and come into existence when there is turmoil, a crisis, a specific issue or event. They lack structure and are associated with violent responses. They use negotiations and dialogue in their quests that are mostly acted internally

These groups use lobbyists that they send to promote their cause. These representatives approach law and policy makers directly and distribute materials related to their purpose. They can also use protests and petitions to further their cause. The groups have many tactics that they use to promote their cause, and therefore have a significant say in law and policy making. Their views and opinions must be sought before a law is passed and enacted. It is these groups that petition laws and head to the courts to have new draconian policies and laws scrapped or blocked from reaching the enforcement stage.

Checks and balances

The lawmaking process in the United States involves many actors and branches owing to the check and balances system. With this system, no branch of the government is more powerful than the other, and each limits the powers of the others. No arm of the government can, therefore, become more powerful than the others. The legislature makes laws that require

presidential assent; The President either signs it into law or objects it. If the law of unconstitutional, the judiciary scraps it. The president checks the judiciary by firing or hiring a new head. This ensures that dictatorship is avoided in the United States and power invested in the hands of the citizens.

References

Cooper, P. J. (2014). *By order of the president: The use and abuse of executive direct action*.

University Press of Kansas.

Gerston, L. N. (2014). *Public policy making: Process and principles*. Routledge.

Neubauer, D. W., & Meinhold, S. S. (2016). *Judicial process: law, courts, and politics in the*

United States. Nelson Education.

Wilson, W. (2017). *Congressional government: A study in American politics*. Routledge.

WILSON, W. (2017). *CONSTITUTIONAL GOVERNMENT IN THE UNITED STATES*.

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